

1-(Undec-10-enoyl)-1,2,3,4,4a,9b-hexahydro-3-oxo-5H-Indeno [1,2-c] pyridazine [II, R=CO(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=O]: To a solution of the foregoing compound (11.2 g, 0.06 mol) in a mixture of ethyl acetate (100 ml) and pyridine (7 g), undec-10-enoic acid chloride (12.1 g) was added dropwise under mechanical stirring at 25°. Stirring was continued for 10 hrs more, excess acid chloride decomposed with water and organic layer separated and washed successively with water, dilute HCl (2N), NaOH (2N) solution and water. The usual processing afforded the desired pyridazine (14.9 g, 70%), m.p. 113-114° (light petroleum); ν (Nujol) 3200 (NH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (amide CO). [Found: C, 82.7; H, 8.3; N, 7.9. C₂₂H₃₀N₂O₂ requires C, 82.4; H, 7.9; N, 8.4%].

1-(11-Undec-10-enyl)-1,2,3,4,4a,9b-hexahydro-5H-Indeno [1,2-c] pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂]: The above amide [II, R=CO(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=O] (10 g, 0.03 mol) dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran (100 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of LAH (3.19 g, 0.09 mol) in THF (100 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 60 hrs, the THF was distilled off completely and the residue decomposed with water. The reaction mixture was extracted with benzene, the extract washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent yielded the desired pyridazine (5.0 g, 50%), b.p. 200°/2 mm; ν 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH). [Found: C, 80.1; H, 10.9; N, 8.6. C₂₂H₃₄N₂ requires C, 80.09; H, 11.32; N, 8.59%].

1-(1-Undec-10-enyl)-2-alkyl-1,2,3,4,5a,4a,9b-hexahydro-5H-indeno [1,2-c] pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R=alkyl, X=H₂]: A mixture of the amine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂; 1.0 g, 0.03 mol], formic acid (2.0 g, 0.04 mol, 90%) and formaldehyde (0.9 g of 40%, 0.012 mol) was heated in an oil bath at 100° for 10 hrs. Excess of formic acid and formaldehyde was removed by distillation. The contents were cooled and basified with ammonia. The liberated base was taken up in benzene and processed as usual to give the pyridazine [R=(CH₂)₉-CH=CH₂, R=CH₃, X=H₂] (0.4 g, 40%), b.p. 140°/1.5 mm.

A mixture of the amine [II, R=(CH₂)₉CH=CH₂, R'=H, X=H₂; 1.0 g, 0.003 mol] and ethyl bromide (0.4 g, 0.0033 mol) was heated on a water bath for 6 hrs. The product was basified with ammonia and processed as usual when the pyridazine [II, R=(CH₂)₉-CH=CH₂; R=C₂H₅, X=H₂] (0.4 g, 35%), b.p. 135-140°/2.5mm was obtained. The corresponding amine with R'=n-C₈H₁₇, b.p. 103°/1.5 mm was obtained in 60% yield. The above three compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis, and they did not show any NH absorption band in their ir spectra.

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Separation and Gravimetric Determination of Niobium and Tantalum with N-o-Tolyl-p-Tertiarybutylbenzohydroxamic Acid**

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THE present paper describes the separation and gravimetric determination of niobium and tantalum with N-o-tolyl-p-tertiarybutylbenzohydroxamic acid (TTBBHA). The method is fairly selective and many of the common ions normally associated with niobium and tantalum do not interfere.

Experimental

N-o-Tolyl-p-tertiarybutylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by the reported method¹. Standard solutions of niobium and tantalum were prepared by the potassium bisulphate, tartaric acid fusion method of Schoeller² and the metal ion content was determined gravimetrically with cupferron³.

General procedure: A suitable aliquot of standard solution of niobium or tantalum was taken. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.0-6.0 for niobium and 0.5-1.5 for tantalum with 10% (v/v) sulphuric acid or 20% (w/v) ammonium acetate. The solution was heated to 60° and 10-20 ml of 2% reagent solution in alcohol was added slowly with constant stirring. The granular precipitate of niobium or tantalum was digested on a hot water bath for 45 minutes. The precipitates of niobium or tantalum complex were filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water and finally with 10% aqueous alcohol to remove traces of the reagent.

The precipitate of niobium complex was dried at 120° to constant weight and weighed as NbO·(C₁₃H₂₀O₂N)₃. The precipitate of tantalum complex was dried at 110° and ignited to pentoxide in a preweighed silica crucible and weighed as Ta₂O₅.

Properties and composition of niobium and tantalum complexes: The freshly precipitated niobium complex was white and crystalline. It was insoluble in water and 10% aqueous alcohol and slightly soluble in chloroform. The niobium complex was thermally

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stable upto 200°. The pure and dried complex was analysed for niobium by ignition of a weighed portion to niobium pentoxide. The carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents were estimated by the usual combustion methods. The niobium complex was found to have the composition $\text{NbO}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ (Found : Nb, 9.71 ; C, 67.98 ; N, 4.23, H, 6.39%. Calcd. Nb, 9.71 ; C, 67.84 ; N, 4.40 ; H, 6.33%).

The tantalum complex was of indefinite composition. It lost weight as the temperature was increased and ultimately converted to the pentoxide at 500°. The complex was insoluble in all the solvent mentioned above.

Effect of pH : Niobium and tantalum were precipitated and determined at different pH following the general procedure described earlier. The results indicated that the precipitation of niobium and tantalum was quantitative in the pH range 4.0 – 6.0 and 0.5 – 1.5 respectively.

Effect of foreign ions : The following ions did not interfere : 200 mg each of alkali metals, Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Be(II), Zn(II), Cr(III), La(III), Ca(III), Mg(II), Al(III), Hg(II), Cd(II), Bi(III), acetate, citrate and carbonate ; 100 mg of V(IV), Th(IV), Ce(III), Zr(IV) and U(VI) ; 50 mg of Mo(IV) and W(VI). However, in the case of niobium, Ti(IV) interfered and Zr(IV) and Ce(IV) had to be masked by EDTA. In determination of tantalum, Ti(IV) and Zr(IV) had to be masked by fluoride and EDTA ; Mo(IV) and W(VI) caused interference.

Separation of niobium and tantalum : The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.5 – 5.5 with 20% ammonium acetate or 10% (v/v) sulphuric acid and niobium was precipitated by slow addition of 2% alcoholic solution of the reagent (10 ml for every 10 mg of metal). The precipitate was digested over hot water bath and niobium was determined as described earlier. The filtrate obtained from the separation of niobium was evaporated to about 200 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 0.5 – 1.5 and the solution was heated to 60°. Tantalum was then precipitated and determined as described earlier.

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Electrochromatographic Studies of Metal Ions on Sn(IV) Hexacyanoferrate(II) Papers : Separation of Metal Ions

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METAL hexacyanoferrates(II) have shown promising characteristics as inorganic ion exchangers¹⁻³. They have been utilized in column^{4,5} and paper⁶ chromatography of metal ions. However, a systematic electrochromatographic study of the common metal ions on papers impregnated with such materials is still lacking. The present paper summarizes our study on Sn(IV) hexacyanoferrate (II) papers which has resulted in some important binary separations.

Experimental

Apparatus : Electrochromatographic studies were performed on Whatman No. 1 paper strips of size 46.4 × 2.5 cm on a horizontal strip apparatus with a regulated power supply.

Preparation of the ion exchange papers : The paper strips were dipped in a 0.1M aqueous solution of Sn(IV) chloride for a few seconds. After drying on a filter paper they were dipped in a 0.1M aqueous solution of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and dried again at room temperature. They were then washed thoroughly in distilled water to remove excess reagents. The strips were finally dried and used as such.

Procedure : The electrophoresis was performed as usual⁷ by taking the various solutions as background electrolytes. The time of migration was fixed as 6 hrs and the potential applied was 100 volts in each case.

Separations achieved : Table 1 summarizes the separations achieved on these papers based on the migration difference.

TABLE 1 — METAL ION SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED IN DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES ON Sn (IV) HEXACYANOFERRATE (II) PAPERS

Electrolyte used	Separation achieved
0.1 M Tartaric acid	Bi-Tl Hg-Tl Ba and Tl from numerous metal ions.
0.1 M Oxalic acid	Se-Mo, Te-Mo, UO_2^{2+} -Mo, Cr-Mo, In-La.
0.1 M Acetic acid	Ba and Sr from numerous metal ions.

Results and Discussion

These studies reveal some interesting features. Some metal ions were taken for their electrochromatographic study in selected media namely 0.1M aqueous